

FULL DETAILS (Read-only) -> [Click Here to Create PDF for Current Dataset of Trial](#)

CTRI No	CTRI/2025/03/083504 [Registered on: 26/03/2025] Trial Registered Prospectively	
Acknowledgement Number	REF/2025/03/100993	
Last Modified On:	13/03/2025	
Post Graduate Thesis	No	
Type of Trial	Observational	
Type of Study Clarification(s) with Reply Modification(s)	Cohort Study	
Study Design	Other	
Public Title of Study Clarification(s) with Reply Modification(s)	Quality of Life and Survival between Surgery and Organ-Preservation Therapy in bladder cancer treatment	
Scientific Title of Study Clarification(s) with Reply Modification(s)	Quality of Life and Evaluation of Survival in Treatment of Bladder Cancer	
Trial Acronym		
Secondary IDs if Any	Secondary ID	Identifier
	NIL	NIL
Details of Principal Investigator or overall Trial Coordinator (multi-center study) Clarification(s) with Reply Modification(s)	Name	Dr Jayanta Chakrabarti
	Designation	Director of Institute and Head of Surgical Oncology
	Affiliation	Chittaranjan National Cancer Institute
	Address	Director Office, Chittaranjan National Cancer Institute, 37 S P Mukherjee Road, Kolkata Kolkata WEST BENGAL 700026 India
	Phone	9836426866
	Fax	
	Email	swayamjayanta@gmail.com
Details Contact Person Scientific Query Clarification(s) with Reply Modification(s)	Name	Dr Debjit Ghosh
	Designation	Assistant Professor & Specialist Grade II
	Affiliation	Chittaranjan National Cancer Institute
	Address	Room no 25, Ground Floor, Department of Radiation Oncology, Chittaranjan National Cancer Institute, 37 S P Mukherjee Road, Kolkata Kolkata Kolkata WEST BENGAL 700026 India
	Phone	7044690778
	Fax	
	Email	debjitghosh15@gmail.com
Details Contact Person Public Query Clarification(s) with Reply Modification(s)	Name	Dr Debjit Ghosh
	Designation	Assistant Professor & Specialist Grade II
	Affiliation	Chittaranjan National Cancer Institute
	Address	Room no 25, Ground Floor, Department of Radiation Oncology, Chittaranjan National Cancer Institute, 37 S P Mukherjee Road, Kolkata Kolkata Kolkata WEST BENGAL 700026 India
	Phone	7044690778
	Fax	
	Email	debjitghosh15@gmail.com
Source of Monetary or Material Support Clarification(s) with Reply Modification(s)	Chittaranjan National Cancer Institute, 37 S P Mukherjee Road, Kolkata, West Bengal, India. PIN 700026	
Primary Sponsor Clarification(s) with Reply Modification(s)	Name	Chittaranjan National Cancer Institute
	Address	Chittaranjan National Cancer Institute, 37 S P Mukherjee Road, Kolkata, West Bengal, India. PIN 700026
	Type of Sponsor	Research institution and hospital
Details of Secondary Sponsor	Name	Address
	NIL	NIL

Countries of Recruitment	India						
Sites of Study Clarification(s) with Reply Modification(s)	No of Sites = 1						
	Name of Principal Investigator	Name of Site	Site Address			Phone/Fax/Email	
	Dr Debjit Ghosh	Chittaranjan National Cancer Institute	Chittaranjan National Cancer Institute, 37 S P Mukherjee Road, Kolkata Kolkata WEST BENGAL			07044690778 debjitghosh15@gmail.com	
Details of Ethics Committee	No of Ethics Committees= 1						
	Name of Committee	Ethics Committee registered with DHR / CDSCO or not	Ethics Committee Registration No.	Approval Status	Date of Approval	Approval Document	Is IEC?
	Institutional Ethics Committee	Yes	CNCI-IEC-JC-2025-03	Approved	11/02/2025	Approval File	No
Regulatory Clearance Status from DCGI	Status		Date		Approval Document		
	Not Applicable		No Date Specified		No File Uploaded		
Health Condition / Problems Studied	Health Type	Condition					
	Patients	(1) ICD-10 Condition: C679 Malignant neoplasm of bladder, unspecified,					
Intervention / Comparator Agent Clarification(s) with Reply Modification(s)	Type		Name	Details			
	Comparator Agent		NIL	NIL			
	Intervention		NIL	NIL			
Inclusion Criteria	Age From	18.00 Year(s)					
	Age To	80.00 Year(s)					
	Gender	Both					
	Details	Patients diagnosed with muscle-invasive bladder cancer (MIBC, cT2-T4aN0M0), eligible for both bladder preservation and radical cystectomy and giving informed consent to participate					
Exclusion Criteria	Details	Patients with metastatic disease (M1) at presentation or having received prior pelvic irradiation or surgery affecting urinary/bowel function or patients unwilling to complete PROM questionnaires					
Method of Generating Random Sequence	Not Applicable						
Method of Concealment	Not Applicable						
Blinding/Masking	Not Applicable						
Primary Outcome	Outcome			TimePoints			
	To compare quality of life (QoL) outcomes between bladder preservation and radical cystectomy patients using validated PROM tools namely Bladder Cancer Index (BCI) & EORTC QLQ-C30			At 3 months, 6 months, 9 months, 12 months and thereafter annually all relevant follow up data and filled PROM questionnaires shall be collected, till completion of this study.			
Secondary Outcome	Outcome			TimePoints			
	To assess overall survival (OS) and progression-free survival (PFS) of patients undergoing bladder preservation versus radical cystectomy & to correlate PROM-derived QoL scores with survival outcomes.			At 3 months, 6 months, 9 months, 12 months and thereafter annually all relevant follow up data and filled PROM questionnaires shall be collected, till completion of this study.			
Target Sample Size	Total Sample Size="140" Sample Size from India="140" Final Enrollment numbers achieved (Total)="Applicable only for Completed/Terminated trials" Final Enrollment numbers achieved (India)="Applicable only for Completed/Terminated trials"						
Phase of Trial	N/A						
Date of First Enrollment (India)	01/04/2025						
Date of Study Completion (India)	Applicable only for Completed/Terminated trials						
Date of First Enrollment (Global)	If country of recruitment is only India, global date would be not applicable.						
Date of Study Completion (Global)	Applicable only for Completed/Terminated trials						
Estimated Duration of Trial	Years="3" Months="0" Days="0"						

Recruitment Status of Trial (Global)	If country of recruitment is only India, global status would be not applicable.
Recruitment Status of Trial (India)	Not Yet Recruiting
Publication Details	N/A
Individual Participant Data (IPD) Sharing Statement	<p>Will individual participant data (IPD) be shared publicly (including data dictionaries)?</p> <p>Response - YES</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What data in particular will be shared? Response - All of the individual participant data collected during the trial, after de-identification. 2. What additional supporting information will be shared? Response - Study Protocol Response - Statistical Analysis Plan Response - Informed Consent Form Response - Clinical Study Report Response - Analytic Code 3. Who will be able to view these files? Response - Anyone 4. For what types of analyses will this data be available? Response - Any purpose. 5. By what mechanism will data be made available? Response - Proposals should be directed to [debjitghosh15@gmail.com]. 6. For how long will this data be available <i>start date provided 01-08-2028 and end date provided 01-08-2033</i>? Response - Beginning 3 months and ending 5 years following article publication. 7. Any URL or additional information regarding plan/policy for sharing IPD? Additional Information - NIL
Result Disclosure	<p>Do you wish to upload results?</p> <p>Response - Summary results have not yet been disclosed</p>
Brief Summary Clarification(s) with Reply Modification(s)	<p>QUEST: Quality of Life and Evaluation of Survival in Treatment of Bladder Cancer</p> <p>A Prospective Study on QoL and Survival of Bladder Cancer Patients Using Patient-Reported Outcome Measurements PROMs</p> <p>Principal Investigator Dr. Jayanta Chakrabarti</p> <p>Co-Investigators Dr. Ranti Ghosh, Dr. Debarshi Lahiri, Dr. Tapas Maji, Dr. Debjit Ghosh</p> <p>Background and Rationale</p> <p>Bladder cancer is one of the most common malignancies worldwide, with muscle-invasive bladder cancer MIBC constituting approximately 25 to 30 percent of newly diagnosed cases. MIBC stage T2-T4a poses a significant clinical challenge, as it requires multimodal treatment strategies to achieve optimal oncological control and maintain quality of life QoL.</p> <p>Evolution of MIBC Management</p> <p>Historically, neoadjuvant chemotherapy followed by radical cystectomy RC emerged as the cornerstone of curative treatment for MIBC. Introduced in the early 20th century, radical cystectomy involves removal of the bladder, surrounding organs, and lymph nodes, often accompanied by urinary diversion procedures such as ileal conduit, continent cutaneous diversion, or neobladder reconstruction. While RC provides effective local control and long-term survival, it is associated with significant perioperative morbidity, impact on urinary and sexual function, and deterioration in overall QoL.</p> <p>Over the past few decades, there has been a paradigm shift towards bladder preservation strategies, driven by advancements in multidisciplinary oncology care. Bladder preservation typically involves trimodal therapy TMT, which combines</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Maximal transurethral resection of bladder tumor TURBT 2. Concurrent chemoradiotherapy CRT 3. Meticulous surveillance to detect recurrence or progression <p>This approach gained traction following landmark studies demonstrating comparable oncological outcomes between bladder preservation and radical cystectomy in well-selected patients. The development of modern radiotherapy techniques, such as image-guided radiotherapy IGRT and intensity-modulated radiotherapy IMRT, has further improved tumor control while minimizing radiation toxicity to adjacent normal tissues. Concurrently, systemic therapies such as gemcitabine-based or cisplatin-based chemotherapy regimens have enhanced the radiosensitizing effects, improving the efficacy of bladder preservation approaches.</p> <p>Bladder Preservation versus Radical Cystectomy The QoL Perspective</p> <p>While survival and disease progression outcomes for TMT and RC are now considered equivalent in selected patients, their impact on QoL is markedly different. Radical cystectomy, despite being curative, often leads to profound changes in urinary, bowel, and sexual function due to the absence of the native bladder and the need for urinary diversion. Conversely, bladder preservation aims to maintain the natural bladder, thereby preserving functional outcomes and improving QoL for many patients.</p> <p>Several studies, including an Indian study, have compared QoL between the two modalities using validated Patient-Reported Outcome Measures PROMs such as the Bladder Cancer Index BCI and the EORTC QLQ-C30. These studies consistently demonstrate that bladder preservation offers superior QoL, particularly in the domains of urinary function, bowel function, and sexual health. However, such data remain limited in the Indian context, where treatment decisions are influenced by socioeconomic, cultural, and logistical factors.</p> <p>Need for the Current Study</p> <p>Given the rising burden of bladder cancer and the increasing adoption of bladder preservation strategies, there is a need for institution-specific data to guide clinical decision-making. At our tertiary care cancer center in eastern India, we manage a substantial number of MIBC patients annually. While previous studies have provided valuable insights into QoL outcomes, there is limited evidence integrating QoL metrics with survival outcomes in a prospective cohort.</p>

Given the large volume of bladder cancer patients treated annually at our center, there is a unique opportunity to replicate this study while also integrating survival outcomes with patient-reported QoL metrics. This will help establish institution-specific data to guide treatment planning and shared decision-making tailored to our patient population.

Objectives

Primary Objective

To compare quality of life QoL outcomes between bladder preservation and radical cystectomy patients using validated PROM tools

- Bladder Cancer Index BCI
- EORTC QLQ-C30

Secondary Objectives

1. To assess overall survival OS and progression-free survival PFS of patients undergoing bladder preservation versus radical cystectomy
2. To correlate PROM-derived QoL scores with survival outcomes

Methods

Study Design

A prospective observational cohort study.

Study Population

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients diagnosed with muscle-invasive bladder cancer MIBC, cT2-T4aN0M0
2. Patients eligible for both bladder preservation and radical cystectomy
3. Age 18 years or older
4. Informed consent to participate

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with metastatic disease M1 at presentation
2. Prior pelvic irradiation or surgery affecting urinary or bowel function
3. Patients unwilling to complete PROM questionnaires

Sample Size

Based on the institutional annual caseload of bladder cancer and the expected response rates for PROMs, a total of n patients will be recruited over a 12-month enrollment period.

Study Groups

Patients will be stratified into two groups based on their treatment choice guided by informed consent forms in their mother tongue, explaining the pros and cons of each choice of modality

- **Group 1** Bladder preservation TURBT plus chemoradiation
- **Group 2** Neoadjuvant chemotherapy followed by radical cystectomy with or without adjuvant therapy

Study Tools

1. Bladder Cancer Index BCI A validated PROM tool measuring urinary, bowel, and sexual QoL domains
2. EORTC QLQ-C30 A global cancer QoL tool assessing functional, symptom, and global health status scales

Note The institution has secured the license to use BCI from the University of Michigan. Translations into local vernacular languages will be validated prior to use.

Data Collection

Baseline Assessment Demographic data, clinical staging, comorbidities, and baseline PROM questionnaires.

Follow-Up Intervals

 PROM assessments will be performed at

3 months
6 months
12 months
Thereafter annually

Survival Data

 Overall survival and progression-free survival will be monitored at regular clinical follow-ups.

Statistical Analysis

- **Descriptive Statistics** Mean, median, and standard deviation for QoL scores
- **Inferential Statistics** Comparison of QoL between groups using t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests. Kaplan-Meier curves for OS and PFS analysis. Cox proportional hazards regression to evaluate the correlation between QoL scores and survival outcomes
- **Software** IBM SPSS version 25

Ethical Considerations

1. **Ethics Approval** The study will be submitted for approval to the Institutional Ethics Committee IEC
2. **Informed Consent** Written informed consent will be obtained from all participants after providing detailed information about the study
3. **Confidentiality** Patient data will be anonymized and stored securely in password-protected systems
4. **PROM Tools** Local vernacular translations will be validated as per standard protocols to ensure cultural appropriateness and linguistic accuracy

Timeline

Phase	Duration
IEC Approval and Study Setup	2 months
Participant Recruitment	12 months
Follow-up and Data Collection	12 months
Data Analysis and Manuscript	6 months

Total Study Duration Approximately 3 years

Expected Outcomes

- A comprehensive comparison of QoL outcomes between bladder preservation and radical cystectomy in our patient population
- Institution-specific survival data correlated with PROM-derived QoL scores
- Insights to inform patient counseling, shared decision-making, and treatment planning